

Sistema de actividades propuesto para desarrollar la competencia intercultural en los estudiantes de Medicina de la Facultad de Medicina "Enrique Cabrera Cossío"

Unit 1 Please call me Beth

Name of activity: introducing yourself or someone.

Topic: hello!

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to introduce themselves and someone, to know about greetings and farewells, asking with WH questions and answering short answers with be.

Procedure:

1- Complete the following text using different grammatical tenses studied.

My name is John Smith, I ----- (be) a diplomatic. I ----- (work) in MINREX for 10 years. I --
----- (graduate) at Raul Roa Garcia Institute. Since I ----- (become) a diplomatic I just -
----- (write) articles about how to resolve political problems in my country. I -----
(always/go) to meetings about interesting topics. Of course, I ----- (wear) a correct code for
dressing. My wife ----- (be) an excellent lawyer, but now she ----- (work) as an English
teacher. We ----- (have) two children, one of them ----- (want) to be a doctor, he ---
----- (have) good marks, so we ----- (think) he ----- (achieve) it. The other one ----
----- (be) only 5 years old, she ----- (dance) all the time, because she ----- (love)
music. My little girl ----- (participate) in a competition of dancing two years ago, and she --
----- (not/win) because she ----- (be) very young. But she ----- (practice) very
hard, because she ----- (try) this year again.

2- Imagine you are a relevant diplomat. Write a letter where you express your future plans to support your country in political terms.

Unidad 2 How do you spend your day?

Name of activity: daily schedules.

Topic: my job.

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to describe their jobs and talk about their daily routines, asking with WH questions and answering short answers with be in simple present.

Procedure:

1. Answer the following questions. Then write a brief paragraph using all this information:

- a) What do you do for a living?
- b) What do your parents do?
- c) What job is dangerous for you? Why?
- d) Where do you work?
- e) Is your job important for humanity? Why?

2. Match column A (jobs and occupations) and column B (explanations)

- | A | B |
|---------------|---|
| 1. Ambassador | a) has the job of designing things. |
| 2. Baker | b) gives lectures, usually in a university. |
| 3. Designer | c) makes bread and cakes and works in a bakery. |
| 4. Bricklayer | d) writes books or novels. |
| 5. Lecturer | e) works with the money and accounts of a |

- | | |
|-----------------|--|
| | company. |
| 6. Accountant | f) helps to build houses using bricks. |
| 7. Travel agent | g) defends people in court and gives legal advice. |
| 8. Judge | h) organizes and sells holidays and flights for other |
| 9. Lawyer | i) decides cases in a law court. |
| 10. Author | j) high official credited to serve as representative of their country. |

3. Read the text and answer the questions:

My name is Lindsay Smith. I'm thirty-two years old. I'm from Canada and I live in Ottawa. I'm an engineer and I work in a big factory. I'm married. My husband's name is Larry. He is thirty-five years old. He is a diplomat. He works in the French embassy here in Canada. He's from France. He speaks French and English. We have two nice sons named Nathan and Noah. Nathan is five and Noah is three years old. We love each other very much. We work long hours but spend the weekend off with our sons. My husband enjoys the city and he thinks that living and working abroad is a great challenge.

(Taken from internet, Wikipedia)

- Where do Lindsay and Larry live?
- Are Lindsay and Larry Americans?
- What are their sons' names?
- How old is each member of the family?
- Are Portuguese and Italian the languages Larry speaks?
- What do they do for a living?

Unit 3 How much is it?

Name of activity: shopping and prices.

Topic: let's buy things!

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to talk about prices, give opinions, make comparisons, buy and sell things, using some demonstratives such as *this, that, these, those*, and ask questions with *how much* and *which*.

Procedure:

1-Write a text talking about the clothes you would choose to go to an important diplomatic dinner in a foreign country using some adjectives. Take into account the large, prices, and comfort.

2-Read the following dialogue (Adapted from Spectrum):

Maggie is shopping for a dress with Lina.

Clerk: May I help you?

Maggie: Yes, I have an important meeting and I need a dress.

Clerk: Well, we have some very nice dresses right over here. I am sure we have one just for you. What size do you wear- a twelve?

Maggie: Oh, no. A fourteen.

Clerk: Fourteen are over there... Oh, look this is beautiful. Don't you think?

Lina: Oh, that's pretty.

Maggie: No, I don't like those flowers. I prefer stripes.

Clerk: But everyone's wearing flowers this year. It's more stylish.

Maggie: Well, not me.

Lina: Oh, what about those over there?

Clerk: The spotted?

Maggie: No, I hate spotted ones.
 Clerk: Well, do you like this?
 Maggie: Hmm...that's not bad. This is nicer. What do you think, Lina?
 Lina: It's beautiful. I like it.
 Maggie: How much is it?
 Clerk: \$450.00.
 Maggie: Oh, no. That's too expensive.
 Lina: Oh, come on. Try on it.
 Maggie: Ok. What do you think?
 Lina: Oh, you look terrific. Everyone is going to love it.
 Maggie: Ok. I take it.

(Taken from internet, Wikipedia)

2.1-Answer the following questions:

- a) What is Maggie looking for? / Maggie is shopping for a dress
- b) Does Maggie like spotted clothes? / No, she doesn't
- c) What's the style of the year? / Flowers.
- d) What's Maggie's size? / Twelve
- e) Does Lina like the four-hundred-fifty-dollars-dress? / Yes, she does.

Unidad 4 Do you like rap?

Name of activity: making invitations.

Topic: would you like to...?

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to talk about *likes* and *deslikes*, *give opinions*, *make invitations and refuse it*, *ask WH questions with do* and *yes or no questions*, pronouns and modal verbs.

Procedure:

1- Read carefully and respond to these invitations. In the case you deny them, give excuses.

- a) I have tickets to go to an interesting English conference. Would you like to go?
- b) Would you like to read about these current news with me? It is important for our work...
- c) What are you going to do this weekend? Would you like to go to a meeting with important personalities?
- d) I am so stressed! Would you like to listen to classical music with me?

1.1- Write three invitations for your best friend or partner.

2- Suppose you want to write invitation cards for your friends to invite them to a conference about current news around the world. Write a card where you express the main points that will be expressed in this conference.

Unidad 5 Tell me about your family

Name of activity: family.

Topic: my family.

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to talk about their family and the different levels at work, using the present continuous through questions and answers.

Procedure:

1-Look at the tree family.

1.1- Fill in the missing word.

- a- Liz is ----- wife.
- b- Tim is----- husband.
- c- Mary and John are Sarah and ----- children.
- d- Sarah is ----- aunt and Simon is his uncle.

1.2- Answer the following questions:

- a- Whose father is Simon?
- b- Whose mother is Liz?
- c- Whose daughter is Sarah?
- d- Whose cousin are Mary and John?

2- Draw a tree, but in this case using the different levels of position or rank in your work.

Unidad 6 How often do you exercise?

Name of activity: family.

Topic: my family.

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to talk about their family and the different levels at work, using the present continuous through questions and answers.

Procedure:

1- Read the following text:

The buzkashi is an equestrian activity practiced in Afghanistan, where it is considered national sport. Although it is practiced in Afghanistan, it is probably originated in Uzbekistán.

It consists in two teams of horsemen, in a field of approximately two kilometers of longitude. The players of each team don't differ in the color of their T-shirt, but rather they seem to know each other. The objective of the game is to take the boz that is a goat without head and extremities, from an end of the field to the other one. The members of both teams struggle to take the body from the goat to the center of the game land. It is a very violent game, it does not have bigger rules and the horsemen finish wrapped in true bloody battles. Neither there are referees for what the result only depends on the players. For the horseman the recompense is the prestige that can have before the rest of the players. The captains, denominated "chapandaz ", with turbans and black beards, they arrive at the court with rifles Kalashnikov to the shoulder and bodyguard and they are shaken hands before beginning the party.

(Taken from internet, Wikipedia)

- a) What is the text about?
- b) Do you read about this sport?
- c) Would you like to practice it?
- d) What do you think about this sport?

- e) Do you consider this sport as rare? Why?
- 2- Tell what the national sport in Cuba is and express your opinion about it.
- 3- Let's discuss about the following topics:
- In what English speaking countries is baseball is popular?
 - What are the differences with its practice in Cuba?

Unidad 7 We had a great time!

Name of activity: a great vacation.

Topic: my last vacation.

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook, video, computer.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to talk about their last vacation, past events, by using the simple past tense and asking and answering with verb *be*.

Procedure:

1-Watch the following video.

(Video taken from an internet program entitled "para aprender inglés: Conversación de Vacaciones Pasadas. Preguntas y Respuestas en Pasado")

Before to watch the video the teacher ask some questions to introduce the topic:

- a- Do you like vacation? Why?
- b- What do you often do on vacation?

During the students watch the video they should answer the following questions:

- a- Did the girl and Bill have a great vacation?
- b- Where did they go?
- c- Was the weather good?
- d- What did they do there?

After students watch the video they should answer the following questions:

- a- When were your last vacation?
- b- Was it great?
- c- What did you do?
- d- Where did you go?
- e- What else could you like to do or go?

2- Write the verbs into the interrogative form of the past simple, then match the questions to the answers.

- 1-What time ----- (you-get up) this morning?
- 2-When ----- (she-move) to London?
- 3-Why----- (he-go) to Paris?
- 4-Where ----- (he-see) the film?
- 5-Whose car ----- (she-drive) this morning?
- 6-Who ----- (they-invite) to dinner?
- 7-What ----- (you-have) for lunch?
- a----- four years ago
- b----- at the cinema
- c----- pizza
- d ----- at 8 o'clock
- e ----- Jean and Tom
- f -----for a holiday
- g ----- Roberts

Unidad 8 What's your neighborhood like?

Name of activity: describing locations.

Topic: amazing places.

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook, video, computer.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to describe locations of places, describe neighborhoods, taking into account prepositions of places.

Procedure:

1-Watch the following video and answer these questions.

Before students watch the video

(Video taken from internet program "para aprender inglés: describing New York City")

- a- Have you travel to another country? Where?
- b- Was a great experience for you? Explain why.
- c- What is the bigger city in the United States?

While watching the video

- a- What is the described?
- b- Is this city one of most famous in the world?
- c- How is call this city?
- d- How is the population in this city?
- e- Are there many interesting places there? Name some of them.

After watching the video

- a- Have been in New York City?
- b- Have you been in this city because of work?
- c- How were your experiences there?

2- Describe your city or neighborhood taking into account the following aspects:

- Location
- Population
- Well know places
- How far or near from here is
- Interesting aspects

Unit 9: What does she look like?

Name of activity: people's appearance.

Topic: people and clothing styles.

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to describe people appearance, identify people, and ask questions to describe people.

Procedure:

1-Write a text talking about your own dress code.

2- Read the following text:

The ambassadors during the acts will follow a certain label, in general, the maxim label suits will be used, because the act is formal and it is required this way:

1. The gentlemen should dress the tuxedo, with tie and vest targets, although they can wear elegant uniforms or the national suit with the personal badges.
2. Ladies wear long dress, to be possible covered, or regional suit as in the case of men.
3. The fixed day and in advance at the signal hour for the Ceremony, the High diplomatic official that is designated will go of uniform, in official automobile to the new Ambassador's residence to accompany him until the Ministry of External Matters (Living room of Ambassadors). In the car, the

new Ambassador will sit down on the right part of the back seat, and the protocol official will sit down on the left. This car will wave the flag of the Ambassador's country.

4. The Ambassador's companions will go to the ceremony in another car that will be usually property of the embassy, and they will go forming a small cortege in caravan until the Ministry of External Matters.

(Taken from internet, Wikipedia: Protocolo diplomático: Ceremonia de Presentación de las Cartas Credenciales. Presentación de las Cartas Credenciales ante un Jefe de Estado)

2.1-) Respond the following questions using the information given in the text:

a- What is the main idea in this text?

b- Do you agree with the information given?

c- Have you participated in one of these ceremonies? Tell your experiences in a brief text in the case to be a positive answer.

d-What do you wear in ceremonies like these?

3-Rewrite these statements using modifiers with participles or prepositions.

a- Jessi is the short woman. She is wearing jeans and boots.

b- Mary is the pretty girl. She is dancing with Tom.

c- Mark is the most attractive men today. He is wearing a beautiful cap.

d- Linda is eating pizza. She is eating next to Diana.

e- Manuel and Michelle are listening to music. They are listening to music on the radio.

Unidad 10 Have you ever ridden a camel?

Name of activity: past experiences.

Topic: experiences learned.

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook, pictures, videos.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to describe past experiences, exchange information about past experiences, by using the present perfect trough questions and answers in this grammatical tense, taking into account the regular and irregular verbs in the past participle.

Procedure

1- During your professional life you have had experiences in conferences, political issues and diplomatic aspects. Exchange with your partner this experience.

2- Show some pictures and videos about a wonderful experience you have had in your career. Explain and tell your partner about it.

Unit 11: It's a very exciting place!

Name of activity: cities around the world.

Topic: Chicago city.

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook, video, computer.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to describe cities, ask and give suggestions, talk about travel and tourism, using adverbs before adjectives, conjunctions and modal verbs, such as, *can* and *should*.

Procedure

1- The following video is about a wonderful city. Let's watch it.

(Video taken from internet program "para aprender inglés: describing Chicago City")

Before students watch the video

a- Have you travelled to the USA?

b- What do you know about the states of this country? What about Illinois?

c- What is the largest city of Illinois?

d- What do you know about this city?

While watching the video

- a- What are some of the famous things in this country?
- b- Is it Chicago bigger than New York City?
- c- What are the most famous places in this city?
- d- What was the tallest building in the world during 25 years?
- e- What is the most popular attraction in the city?
- f- Why is this city a changing city?

After watching the video

Let's watch the video again and find another way of saying:

-largest

-attraction

-in fact

1.1-Role play.

A: suppose you are a Cuban diplomat and you should travel to Chicago to meet with an ambassador to debate about political issues.

B: suppose you are an important diplomat in Chicago. You help a Cuban diplomat describing him how Chicago is, because this information is important for a meeting with an ambassador.

2- Read the text and answer the following questions:

Capitol of Havana, undisputed tourist attraction

One of the most interesting tours in Havana is to visit to the Capitol of Havana, which, while still undergoing renovation, already hosts many pilgrims from all over the planet. A site built to house the Cuban Parliament (National Assembly of the Popular Power), it is of incomparable beauty and has a history that all should get to know. With its dome marking the silhouette of a modern and cosmopolitan city, the site also has a diamond marker of the kilometer zero of the country's roads, symbol of the development of transportation. The property occupies an area of 388.700 square meters between the streets Paseo del Prado, Dragones, Industria and San Jose, and was inaugurated on May 20, 1929. Right around it, there are places of interest for tourist, such as, the Royal Tobacco Factory of Partagás, Central Park, Fountain of the Indian Woman, Jose Marti Promenade. Its construction lasted three years, two months and days, and the work was directed by the architect Eugenio Raynieri Piedra. 8000 people participated in its building and the total value reached 17 million pesos.

(Taken from the magazine "Cuba plus": Capitol of Havana, undisputed tourist attraction. Page 16.

Written by Roberto F. Campos)

- a- What is the most interesting tour in Havana City?
- b- Why was this place built?
- c- What does the diamond inside mark? What is its importance?
- d- What is the area that this place occupy?
- e- When was this building built?
- f- What other amazing places are there around this building?
- g- How much did building late to be built?
- h- How was the architect of this wonder?
- i- Did many people participate in this construction?
- j- Was very expensive this construction? Why?

Unidad 12 It really works!

Name of activity: health problems.

Topic: how do you feel today?

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to talk about health problems, ask and give advice, using some modal verbs.

Procedure

1-Interpret the following phrase:

"The health is measured by the impact that a person can receive without committing her system of life. This way, the system of life becomes approach of health". A healthy person is who can live her dreams admitted fully"....

Moshé Feldenkrais

(Taken from internet, Wikipedia)

a-What do you think about it? Explain

b-Do you like it? Why?

2- Research about the worst health problem for you in a country you have visited. Write a large text with this information.

Unidad 13 May I take your order?

Name of activity: food

Topic: eating delicious food.

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to express likes and dislikes, order a meal, using modal verbs.

Procedure

1-List of healthy eating habits to adapt from 3 countries around the world.

Chinese culture	Chowing down with chopsticks can slow down eating, less food and fewer calories.
Ethiopia culture	A flatbread made of teff flour which is high in fiber, Vitamin C and protein. Big family style meals which make it hard to control portions, individual servings make it easier to see how much they are eating.
French culture	The French have one of the lowest obesity rates in the world, they live the longest despite the rich food, the love full fat cheese, yogurt, butter, bread and chocolate. The secret their portions are small, they don't snack, walk a lot and eat very slowly. Red wine in moderation Bottom line it's not what they eat, it's how they eat

(Taken from internet: Wikipedia)

1.1-Take notes and be ready to talk about healthy eating habits in China, Ethiopia and France.

a-Say which country you think has the best eating habit. Why?

b-Which one would you start practicing from now?

c-Which is the weirdest dinning etiquette? Why?

d- Which one do you think that doesn't make any sense? Why?

e-What should you never do when in Cuba?

2-Answer the following questions:

- a-Are you a good cook? What is your speciality?
- b-What is your favorite fruit or vegetable?
- c-What do you think of British food?
- d-What is a typical dish in your country?
- e-Who does the cooking in your family?
- f-What did you eat yesterday?
- g-How often do you eat out?
- h-Are for or against fast food?
- i-Have you ever been on a diet?
- j-Have you ever tried Greek or Japanese food?
- k-Where do you buy your food?

2.2- Write a text with all this information.

3- Describe your favorite food.

-What ingredients are in it?

-Why is it your favorite?

-How often do you eat it?

3.3- Write a text with the responses.

Unit 14: The biggest and the best!

Name of activity: countries.

Topic: describing countries.

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to describe countries, make comparisons, express opinions, talk about distance and measurements, using comparatives and superlatives forms of adjectives.

Procedure

1- Read this telephone conversation:

A: Tourist information. Can I help you?

B: Yes, please. I am coming to Wentbridge this weekend, and I am looking for a good hotel.

A: Well, the Scotsman is the oldest hotel in Wentbridge, but it is also the most expensive. The Castle is the most beautiful. The Prince is the newest and the biggest.

A: How about the comfort?

B: The Prince is more comfortable than the Scotsman because is newer than the other. The attention to the clients in the Scotsman is friendlier than the Castle.

A: Where is the bigger pool?

B: The Prince has a huge pool. It is the bigger pool.

A: Ok, thanks, I'll go to this one, because for me is more important a good pool to swim than a good attention.

(Taken from internet, Wikipedia)

1.1-Answer the following questions:

- a) Where does the man go?
- b) What is the man looking for?
- c) Is the Castle the oldest hotel in Wentbridge?
- d) What is the most expensive hotel there?
- e) Is the Prince the newest and the biggest?
- f) What is the most comfortable hotel?
- g) How is the attention to the clients in Scotsman?
- h)What hotel has the bigger pool?

i) Where does the man decide to stay? Why?

2- Complete the questions using the comparative or superlative degrees of the adjectives as required.

a. Which country is _____, Guyana or Jamaica? (big)

b. What country is _____ in Europe? (big)

c. Which river is _____, Almendares, Toa or Cauto? (long)

d. Which river is _____, Mississippi or Amazon? (long)

e. Which city is _____ in Canada, Toronto, Ottawa or Montreal? (crowded)

f. What city is _____ in Cuba? (crowded)

g. Which mountain is _____, Kilimanjaro, Mount Everest or Mount McKinley? (high)

f. What mountain is _____ in Cuba? (high)

h. What country is _____, United Kingdom, Australia or New Zealand? (interesting)

g. Which city is _____, Sydney or Montego Bay? (interesting)

3. Write a text comparing Cuban provinces and cities or two English speaking countries. (80 words).

Unidad 15 I'm going to a soccer match

Name of activity: invitations and excuses.

Topic: let's go out.

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to talk about plans, make invitations, accept and refuse invitations, take and leave messages, using the future tense.

Procedure

1-Read carefully this story:

When I was a little girl, I wanted to be a stewardess, it was my dream for years. But, one day, in a History lesson, I learnt about the past in my country, so from that day to nowadays, I decided to study policy. Policy is something interesting, relative to the reorganization of a country. I love my country, so I will take care my land being a diplomatic.

(Text written by the author of the research)

a-What is the main idea in this text?

b-Interpret this text.

c-How about you? What is your professional story?

d-Is your story similar with this?

1.1-Respond all this items in a brief text.

2-Write a text about how you suppose Cuba should be in 20 years.

Unit 16: A change for the better!

Name of activity: changes.

Topic:

Material: board, Interchange book, notebook.

Objective: at the end of the lesson the students should be able to exchange personal information, describe changes, talk about future plans, using the simple present, past and present perfect tense.

Procedure

1- Read this article:

The Democratic Christian Party of Cuba is a democratic Christian political party in Cuba. Although the changes in the Constitution of Cuba in 1992 legalized the act of the formation of political parties different from the Communist Party of Cuba, these parties are not authorized to make campaign or to participate in any public political activity in the island. The Christian Democratic Party has the biggest structure within Cuban opposition. A small section within the party formed a new political

organization called Christo Del Rey in 1996. The President of the Democratic Christian Party of Cuba is the Cuban exiled Marcelino Miyares Sotolongo and the international secretary is José Ignacio Rasco, also in the exile. Rasco, founder of the Cuban Christian Democratic Party in 1959, is a professor, writer and columnist. He is also the President of Jacques Maritain Institute of Cuba and of the Cuban Editorial House. The manifest of the party, created in Miami 1991, points out: "We have taken the decision of founding the Democratic Christian Party of Cuba because we want to offer a political alternative to our homeland in the fight for the human rights, the economic development and the social justice from a democratic and pluralistic perspective. The party invokes Simón Bolívar and José Martí's legacy, who conceived Latin America as a common, shared fraternity of nations and sovereign". The Democratic Christian Party of Cuba is openly against all foreign intervention in Cuba, and they declare its opposition to the seizure by United States.

(Taken from internet, Wikipedia)

1.1-Taking into account the information given in the text respond:

a- Have you ever read about the Democratic Christian Party of Cuba?

b- Do you believe in this party or religion?

c- Do you think is it important for our country?

d-What do you know about José Ignacio Rasco?

e-What do you think about the phrase expressed by Rasco?

f- What do you consider about this article? Do you think this party aims at "a change for the better"?

Give reasons.

2-Write an article with your responses to the contents of the previous work.